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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this report; “D4.7: Policy brief including policy recommendations” is to deliver a comprehensive public report collating policy-relevant lessons learned during the INDUSAC project and of importance at regional and EU level. Following its submission, this report should not only assist European policymakers in the formation of future policies related to industry-academia collaboration, but also organisations and institutions that wish to explore opportunities and further research related to the topic.

This report has been developed during the final months of the INDUSAC project, using research and input collected throughout the project lifetime. While the partner responsible for the authorship of this report (Bax) has composed it, contributions from all partners within the INDUSAC consortium have been valuable, as well as inputs gathered from external stakeholders including students, researchers, company representatives, European Commission policymakers, and attendees of the INDUSAC final event. All contributions are greatly appreciated and ensure the consideration of diverse perspectives in the formation of this policy brief.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT	3
ABSTRACT	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
1. INTRODUCTION.....	6
2. SUMMARY OF INDUSAC FINDINGS.....	7
1. The potential of similar initiatives	7
2. The need for a centralised platform	7
3. The need for a mobile app.....	7
4. Quick, small-scale projects are attractive.....	8
5. Companies value the access to top talent.....	8
6. Financial reward for students	8
7. Researchers value the process.....	8
3. SUMMARY OF POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	9
1. Scale up and Institutionalise Agile Co-Creation Mechanisms.....	9
2. Create a Centralised EU Platform for Co-Creation Projects.....	9
3. Consider Financial and Non-Financial Incentives for All Participants.....	10
4. Use Co-Creation as a Talent Pipeline Strategy	11
CONCLUSION.....	13

1. INTRODUCTION

With rapidly developing technologies, rising global competition, and the emergence of complex political and economic challenges worldwide, the European Union must take action to stay strong and competitive. The Draghi (2024) report, *The Future of European Competitiveness*, warned that without taking measures to strengthen its innovation capacity, industrial resilience, and strategic autonomy, Europe risks falling behind.

At the heart of the strategy to preserve Europe's competitiveness with global powers such as the United States and China lies an underleveraged asset: Industry-Academia collaboration. While European universities are globally recognised as leading institutions for innovation and high-quality research, the region struggles to convert breakthrough research into scalable industrial initiatives.

To address this issue, the European Commission has dedicated significant funds into R&D investment and new mechanisms to align public research with strategic industrial goals, funding initiatives such as the INDUSAC project, among many others.

If Europe truly wishes to remain competitive, innovative, and independent, it must continue to strengthen the ties between knowledge and industry. This collaboration is essential for the EU's future.

2. Summary of INDUSAC Findings

Since its launch in September 2022, the INDUSAC project has focused on designing, piloting, and validating a new model for fast, human-centred collaboration between students, researchers, and companies across Europe.

Through extensive research carried out during the project lifetime and the lived experiences of the project implementation, partners have been able to gather a series of findings that can be used to inform policy recommendations concerning future industry-academia collaboration in Europe.

Many elements have been fed back to the INDUSAC consortium through anonymous internal surveys, questionnaires to participants in the INDUSAC mechanism, and contributions during the collaborative final event. These include:

1. The potential of similar initiatives

Mechanisms connecting industry and academia, such as the one developed during the INDUSAC project have serious potential if the process and platform can be further streamlined and additional funding made available.

2. The need for a centralised platform

While there was general satisfaction with the INDUSAC mechanism experience, feedback from both sides (industry and academia) expressed the need for a “one-stop-shop” platform, where challenges can be submitted and applied to, while contact between companies, co-creation teams, and INDUSAC support is easily facilitated.

3. The need for a mobile app

With the concept of the mobile office now very prevalent, the need for a mobile app version of the INDUSAC platform was mentioned. This way, all involved parties can maintain regular communication and ease in participating in the INDUSAC experience.

4. Quick, small-scale projects are attractive

A key positive element from the INDUSAC experience was the size of the projects. One of the most attractive features of the mechanism for companies and students / researchers was the opportunity to work on small, quick projects over the space of a number of weeks, rather than long, drawn out processes that could take several months to complete.

5. Companies value the access to top talent

For companies, access to talent was identified as the most attractive aspect of participation in INDUSAC. Companies are generally interested in the innovative ideas and insights that top students can provide.

6. Financial reward for students

For students, the opportunity to earn money, and enhance their CV / Resumé was listed as a primary benefit and attraction to participate in the initiative. While some students acknowledged the benefits of partaking in a co-creation project without the prospect of financial reward for their work, many admitted that they would be much less likely to participate if the opportunity for payment was removed.

7. Researchers value the process

Feedback from researchers was generally positive, and they valued the opportunity to put their research and experience into practice in real-world settings. However, several expressed that they would appreciate and welcome financial reward for their work. The lack of financial reward was identified as a barrier for more researchers to involve themselves in INDUSAC.

3. Summary of Policy Recommendations

The findings collected during the INDUSAC project and outlined in the previous section of this report can be used to inform a series of recommendations for policymakers working on the topic of industry-academia collaboration. This section will outline the key recommendations, with the objective of contributing to the continued research and development of this topic, as Europe continues to prioritise competitiveness in the coming years. These recommendations are aligned with the objectives of the European Code of Recommendation for Knowledge Valorisation, which emphasises the translation of research results into societal and economic value through collaborative, inclusive, and impact-oriented approaches.

1. Scale up and Institutionalise Agile Co-Creation Mechanisms.

The first recommendation is for the establishment of a permanent, EU-backed mechanism that supports small-scale, quick co-creation projects between academia and industry, taking lessons and learnings from the experience of the INDUSAC project.

The success and establishment of the INDUSAC mechanism, combining a comprehensive methodology with an online matchmaking platform demonstrated that short, agile project cycles are highly attractive and manageable for companies and student teams, offering quick collaborations, mutual learning, and fast feedback loops. The model is proven to reduce barriers to entry and encourage continuous collaboration, particularly for SMEs and first-time participants in EU-funded initiatives.

Such mechanisms should be explicitly framed as instruments to accelerate the valorisation of research results, skills, and data through early engagement with industry and society. Actioning this recommendation could involve the introduction of regular funding calls for quick co-creation projects across key strategic innovation areas, with simplified administrative requirements and clearly defined valorisation objectives. Policymakers should identify priority sectors and policy challenges aligned with EU industrial and societal strategies, ensuring that co-creation efforts contribute to both competitiveness and public value.

2. Create a Centralised EU Platform for Co-Creation Projects

The development of a centralised, EU-supported digital platform for industry-academia collaboration where challenges, calls, matchmaking, and communication channels are unified could also alleviate the need for the additional and potentially fragmented funding of similar research and innovation projects. If European policymakers are satisfied that the INDUSAC project sufficiently developed and validated a functional model for co-creation, it can be justified that the European Commission moves to centralise and scale such a platform to continue progress in this area.

Feedback from INDUSAC participants highlighted that communication was occasionally challenging due to the need for multiple channels and platforms. A centralised platform would streamline access, improve transparency, and increase engagement, while management of the platform by the Commission would increase trust, visibility, and alignment with EU knowledge valorisation objectives.

Action points for this recommendation would be to support or facilitate the design, development, and launch of an EU-wide portal for challenge submissions, team formations, communication, document management, mentoring, evaluations, and the management and transfer of FSTP funds. In accordance with the Code of Recommendation for Knowledge Valorisation, the platform should also provide clear guidance on intellectual asset management, data sharing, and exploitation pathways. An additional consideration or further development would be the implementation of multilingual support systems in order to improve user experience across member states and associated countries.

Users would also be likely to appreciate the development of a mobile app for any platform of this kind, allowing real-time engagement and flexibility. In this day, where hybrid working is the norm, the lack of a mobile platform would limit accessibility, especially for students and early-career professionals and researchers. This enhancement was a recurring feedback point from INDUSAC participants.

3. Consider Financial and Non-Financial Incentives for All Participants

The experience of and feedback from the INDUSAC project revealed that students and researchers in co-creation projects strongly value financial compensation, while also recognising the importance of formal recognition of their efforts. Ensuring equitable incentives across future initiatives can increase motivation, widen participation, and

reinforce the perception of co-creation as a credible professional activity rather than an extracurricular add-on.

For policymakers, the introduction of a mandate to ensure fair compensation in all future EU-funded co-creation calls could alleviate this issue, while allowing the EU to focus on providing researchers working on cutting-edge topics with real-world experience to put their concepts into practice. In parallel, and in line with the Code of Recommendation for Knowledge Valorisation, non-financial incentives should be strengthened. These could include the formal recognition of co-creation activities within higher education curricula, the award of ECTS credits for students, and the integration of co-creation outputs into learning outcomes for relevant degree programmes.

Furthermore, should the European Commission wish to prioritise the development of researchers in line with the objective of increased European competitiveness, greater integration of co-creation activities into researcher assessment and performance evaluation frameworks would significantly lower barriers to participation. Policymakers should encourage universities and research organisations to recognise involvement in co-creation projects as a contribution to knowledge valorisation, societal impact, and innovation performance, complementing traditional metrics such as publications and citations. Where direct financial compensation is not feasible, recognising co-creation as part of workload allocation, career progression, or institutional performance indicators could provide a meaningful alternative incentive.

4. Use Co-Creation as a Talent Pipeline Strategy

Companies involved in the INDUSAC project and final event consistently reported that access to top academic talent was one of the most valuable aspects of participation, while students highlighted the benefits of skills development, exposure to real-world challenges, and improved employability. Embedding this dimension more explicitly into future initiatives can improve industry buy-in and long-term sustainability.

To substantiate co-creation as a talent pipeline strategy, future European Commission-supported initiatives should more explicitly link participation in co-creation projects to career development and recruitment pathways. This could include mechanisms such as structured internships or traineeships following successful co-creation projects, visibility of participant profiles to companies through centralised platforms, and follow-up matchmaking events focused on employment opportunities.

From a policy perspective, co-creation experiences could also be better integrated into formal education pathways by encouraging higher education institutions to embed industry-driven challenges into curricula, capstone projects, or doctoral training programmes. For companies, participation could be framed not only as a short-term innovation opportunity, but also as a strategic investment in future human capital, aligned with skills needs and workforce development strategies.

By supporting partnerships between universities, research organisations, business clusters, and companies, the European Commission can foster a structured transition from academia to industry. Any model backed at EU level is likely to increase credibility and participation, particularly when aligned with the objectives of the Code of Recommendation for Knowledge Valorisation, which promotes the development of skills, entrepreneurship, and long-term collaboration as key enablers of impact.

Conclusion

The INDUSAC project has demonstrated the significant potential of structured, quick, agile collaboration between industry and academia. The success of the initiative combined with the feedback received from participants, and taking into consideration the lessons learned, demonstrates that with the right mechanisms in place – such as quick co-creation cycles, a centralised platform, fair and balanced financial incentives, and clear pathways from academia to industry – Europe can benefit from more effective industry-academia collaboration in the years ahead.

The INDUSAC methodology demonstrated clear value for participating companies, particularly SMEs and start-ups by providing them with access to innovative ideas from interdisciplinary student and research teams from across the region, the low-risk exploration of solutions without the need for significant financial or time investment, and, in certain cases, talent scouting opportunities, with several companies identifying potential future hires.

The recommendations outlined in this report provide a roadmap for policymakers seeking to build on INDUSAC's achievements in alignment with the European Code of Recommendation for Knowledge Valorisation. By continuing to invest in and institutionalise co-creation models of this nature, the European Commission has the opportunity to embed industry-academia collaboration as a strategic pillar of Europe's innovation agenda, supporting competitiveness, societal impact, and the development of future talent.

Moving forward, further investment and coordination will be key to maximising the value of future initiatives. As Europe continues to prioritise competitiveness, collaboration, and resilience, the lessons from INDUSAC should inform future policy and programme design and development. Should the recommendations in this report be considered when taking the next step in Europe's path towards effective partnerships between industry and academia, the topic will not just be supported, but embedded as a strategic pillar of the European Union's innovation agenda.

I. LIST OF REFERENCES

(includes referenced deliverables, datasets, articles, web pages)

- Draghi, M. 2024. The Future of European Competitiveness. September 2024. European Union, 2025
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